

Neurorehabilitation in the times of Covid-19: insights from the Spanish Neurorehabilitation Society (SENR)

[S. Laxe](#), [J. Ferri](#), [A. Juárez-Belaunde](#), [M. Ríos-Lago](#), [R. Rodríguez-Duarte](#) & [M. Murie-Fernández](#)

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ABSTRACT

The entire world is experiencing an unprecedented global health crisis and Spain has been one of the most heavily affected countries within Europe. Unexpected rapid changes and reorganization of medical services that occurred during the pandemic lead to an impact in the practice of neurorehabilitation. The idiosyncrasies typical of neurorehabilitation management, specially in acute facilities, that makes it susceptible as a vector of dissemination of Covid but also because of the need of finding new wards and intensive care units for Covid patients, the interventions in neurorehabilitation has suffered enormous changes. There is a need for rethinking the future to treat a new wave of patients with neurorehabilitation necessities such as those recovering from Covid 19 with neurological sequelae but also of those neurorehab patients who were unable to access the health system during the locke down period. This article is intended to invite to reflect on and discuss the redesign of our current neurorehabilitation plans after the experience on the Covid 19 pandemic.

KEYWORDS:

- [Neurorehabilitation](#)
- [Covid 19](#)
- [SARS-Cov2](#)